

Perceptual Acquisition of Arabic Emphatic Consonants in the L2: Is Pharyngealisation Enough?

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Abstract. Arabic features a phonological distinction between plain consonants /s/, /ð/, /t/, and /d/, and their emphatic counterparts /sʕ/, /ðʕ/, /tʕ/, and /dʕ/ which are variously described as pharyngealised or uvularised. Distinguishing these phoneme pairs constitutes a major obstacle for English-speaking learners of Arabic; didactic material often suggests English speakers to attend to coarticulatory cues of emphasis on adjacent vowels rather than the consonant itself. English-speaking learners of Arabic were presented with a binary forced identification task of Modern Standard Arabic CVC pseudowords. The audio stimuli were cross-spliced so that only some segments were contextually emphatic in order to examine whether emphatic perception makes use of acoustic cues from the target emphatic consonant, the vowel, or the non-target consonant. Results suggest that emphatic effects on vowels are the most salient perceptual cue for English speakers, especially when paired with a target emphatic. Non-target consonants had no effect. Manner of articulation effects were observed as emphatic plosives elicited more accurate responses (particularly of /t/-/tʕ/). Vowel quality was also a predictor of emphatic responses as participants were most accurate for stimuli including /a/. These effects evidence the notion that English speakers make use of L1 contrasts (/t/-/d/ and /æ/-/ɑ/ in this case) to acquire nonnative phonemes. No effects of proficiency or pedagogical background were observed. The results provide support for the Extended Native Language Magnet Model (NLM-e) of acquisition. Implications and suggestions for future research are presented.

Keywords: phonology; language acquisition; Arabic; pharyngealisation

1 Introduction

1.1 Emphatic Consonants

Most Semitic languages feature a series of emphatic consonants that are phonemically distinct from plain consonants (Table 1). Emphatic and plain consonants form frequent minimal pairs (e.g., *dalla* ‘to indicate’ vs. *dalla* ‘to go astray’).

Arabic emphatics are articulated with dorsal constriction. The exact phonetic status of Arabic emphatics is debated and will be explored in Section 1.1.1. To avoid phonetic uncertainty, convention advises an underdot to represent emphasis (e.g., plain /s/ vs. emphatic /sʕ/). This notation is used throughout this paper.

Table 1: *Phoneme inventory of Modern Standard Arabic (MSA). Where there are two consonants in one cell, the left is plain and the right is emphatic. Marginal/debated phonemes in brackets.*

Information adapted from Thelwall and Sa’Adeddin (1990) and Mustafawi (2017)

<u>MSA Consonants</u>		Labial	Inter-dental	Alveolar	Postalv-eolar	Velar	Uvular	Laryngeal
Nasal	Voiced	m		n				
Plosive	Voiceless			t ṭ		k	q	ʔ
	Voiced	b		d Ḍ				
Fricative	Voiceless	f	θ	s ṣ	ʃ	x ~ χ		ħ
	Voiced		ð ḏ	z		ʁ ~ ʁ		ʕ
Affricate	Voiced				dʒ			

Approximant	Voiced	w		l (l)	j		
Trill	Voiced			r (r)			

<u>MSA Vowels</u>	Front	Back
High	i i:	u u:
Low	æ æ:	ɑ ɑ:

There are four uncontroversial emphatics. These are the coronals /s/, /t/, /d/, and /ð/ which are often referred to as the primary emphatics (Jaber et al., 2019). They are produced with dorsal articulation in contrast to their non-emphatic counterparts. Primary emphatics also trigger backed allophones of adjacent vowels. The most noticeable of these is /a/ which is generally [æ] (Alghamdi, 1998; Al-Bataineh, 2019) but is pronounced as [ɑ] proximal to emphatics (Ferguson, 1997; Bukshaisha, 1985). Realisations of /d/ and /ð/ vary across dialects. Egyptian and Moroccan dialects realise /ð/ as [z] (Broselow, 1976; Freeman, 2015), Levantine dialects merge them to [d] (Al-Essa, 2022) whereas Algerian, Qatari, and Yemeni Arabic merge them to [ð] (Slimani, 2018; Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023; Watson, 1999). In fact, Al-Wer (2003) asserts that no spoken colloquial variety maintains both /d/ and /ð/. For the sake of consistency, this paper focuses on Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) as a ‘neutral’ register that crucially contains all four of the primary coronal emphatics.

/q/ is occasionally considered a primary emphatic. Al-Solami (2013) suggests that coronal emphatics and uvulars (/q/, /χ/, /ʁ/) pattern together phonologically as only coronal emphatics and uvulars trigger nasal place assimilation. Furthermore, Gulf Arabic sometimes features *ghawa syndrome* in which guttural consonants cannot be syllable-final; this does not apply to coronal emphatics nor /q/ (Huneety et al., 2024; Taqi, 2018), see also prohibitions on roots with two gutturals that does not apply for emphatics or /q/, e.g., √qtʁ ‘to cut’.

Therefore, phonologically, the emphatic consonant inventory seems to include /q/. However, many colloquial dialects merge /q/ with /ʔ/, /g/, or /k/ (Jabbari, 2013; Sallam 1980; Saadane & Nabash, 2015) so [q] does not often occur in spoken language. Some dialects (e.g., Saffarini) feature emphatic /k/ as distinct from /q/ (Saleh & Golston, 2019).

Other ‘secondary emphatics’ exist in some contexts (Jaber et al., 2019). Secondary emphatics include sounds such as /m b f x k/ that appear sparsely throughout Arabic dialects (e.g., Harrell, 1957; Cowell, 1964). They tend not to form minimal pairs with their plain analogues. Although Jaber et al. (2019) assert this is true for Urban Jordanian Arabic, Youssef (2014) finds a small number of minimal pairs in Cairene Arabic, e.g., *jaṃṃa* ‘mother!’ vs. *jamma* ‘direction’. Even in these cases, these are highly marginal phonemes appearing in one or two native words each, e.g., *ṃajja* ‘water’ and *ṃama* ‘mother’ (*jaṃṃa* < *ja ṃama* where *ja* is a vocative particle).

The emphatic /r/ and /l/ are the most proposed secondary emphatics (Jaber, 2001). /l/ is perhaps the more marginal of the two (Younes, 1994). It appears in most dialects in the word for ‘God’, *Allāh*. This does form minimal pairs: *wallāhu* ‘and God’ vs. *wallāhu* ‘he appointed him’ in Classical Arabic (this is also a minimal pair in MSA) or *lla* ‘God’ vs. *lla* ‘no’ in Moroccan Arabic (Ferguson, 1956). Other than this, most occurrences of [l] are due to coarticulation with a nearby primary emphatic (Al-Bataineh, 2019). [r] has a similar status: it appears in a handful of words and most often as a backed allophone of /r/. However, /r/ seems to phonologically pattern with emphatics. Some verbs show an inflectional pattern of *yiCCiC* in the perfect. The second /i/ is instead /u/ when adjacent to an emphatic or /r/ (2):

(1) a.	<i>katab</i>	<i>yiktīb</i>	‘he wrote’
	<i>xabaz</i>	<i>yixbīz</i>	‘he baked’
b.	<i>xabaṭ</i>	<i>yixbuṭ</i>	‘he struck’
	<i>barad</i>	<i>yibrud</i>	‘he became cold’

(data adapted from Younes, 1994)

It may also form minimal pairs: *raff* ‘shelf’ vs. *raff* ‘it twitched’ in Cairene and *rāyib* ‘curdled’ vs. *rāyib* ‘collapsed’ in Moroccan Arabic (Youssef, 2019). As minimal pairs exist, both /l/ and /r/ may be awarded the title of marginal phonemes. However, they phonologically differ from primary emphatics in that they are often de-emphasised, especially in proximity to /i/ (e.g., *wallahu* ‘and God’ vs. *bismillah*; *rayyisna* ‘our president’ vs. *riyāsa* ‘presidency’).

Youssef (2019) suggests there are three types of Arabic dialect in this regard. Western dialects (e.g., Egyptian, and Moroccan) are split-R dialects in which /r/ and /r̥/ are distinctive phonemes. Levantine dialects are emphatic-R as they feature /r̥/ with [r̥] and [r] as allophones with complementary distribution. And Gulf dialects are plain-R with /r/ featuring complementary plain and emphatic allophones.

Due to the marginal and dialectal nature of the secondary emphatics as detailed above, they will be excluded from the term *emphatic*. /q/ will be excluded for the latter of these reasons as well as its unique articulation in relation to /k/. Unlike the coronal emphatics, /q/ does not differ from /k/ only in *secondary* articulation; /q/ features primary articulation at the uvula rather than the velum like /k/. This makes comparison of /q/ and /k/ more difficult as more features differ. Thus, *emphatic* here refers only to /s/, /t/, /d/ and /ð/.

1.1.1 Articulatory and Acoustic Characteristics of Emphatics

In terms of emphatic articulation, the most common stance is that they are pharyngealised as supported by articulatory studies (Davis, 1995; Al-Ani, 1970). However, there is growing literature to suggest that emphatics are uvularised. Al-Solami (2013) identifies articulatory similarities between uvulars and emphatics such as that the entire tongue body retracts in both cases. Other investigations (Zawaydeh, 1999; Ghazeli, 1997) have used physiological evidence (e.g., endoscopic and cinefluorographic imaging) to identify the locus of constriction in emphatic consonants as the upper pharynx, by the uvula. Although others have identified emphatics as velarised (Obrecht, 1968), the primary articulatory debate, especially in the modern day, is between uvularisation and pharyngealisation.

Altairi et al. (2017) used ultrasound to isolate which muscles are responsible for uvularisation and pharyngealisation. They found that uvulars and primary emphatics featured backing caused by the styloglossus, a muscle that pulls the tongue up and back towards the uvula. Pharyngeal constriction was instead found to be associated with contraction of the hyoglossus, the complementary muscle that pulls the tongue down and back. This groups emphatics with uvulars rather than pharyngeals.

Often, uvularisation and pharyngealisation are not distinguished; even the IPA uses /ʕ/ for both. Some studies (Herzallah, 1990; Alioua, 1995; Yeou, 1997; Zawaydeh, 1999) suggest that emphatic constriction occurs at a point around the oropharynx and is consistent with both uvularisation and pharyngealisation. Although not clearly separable, Arabic features uvular and pharyngeal consonants, so isolating how emphatics pattern phonetically with these natural classes is important.

The acoustic properties of emphasis may be investigated to isolate the type of constriction present (Stevens & House, 1955). The consensus of production literature suggests that emphasis is directly associated with a significant lowering of F2 in the consonant and surrounding segments (Aldamen & Al-Deaibes, 2023; Jongman et al., 2011; Zawaydeh, 1999; Yeou, 1997; Al-Solami, 2013; Ali & Daniloff 1974; Card, 1983; Obrecht, 1970 among others). Boxberger (1981) finds a decrease of around

650 Hz in F2 transition frequencies of emphatic consonants. This varies significantly depending on the consonant, the adjacent vowels, and the consonant's position in a syllable. Card (1983) instead finds a lower reduction in F2 of around 200-300 Hz. A depressed second formant is consistent with constriction at the uvula (Zawaydeh & de Jong, 2011) as a "straightforward result of tongue retraction" (Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023:8). Uvular constriction lengthens the horizontal oral cavity, reducing F2 (Lieberman, 2007). A similar depressed F2 is found during and following uvular consonants (Zawaydeh & de Jong, 2011). This acoustic data points to uvularised emphatics.

Another acoustic correlate of emphasis is raised F1 (Jongman et al., 2011; Zawaydeh, 1999; Yeou, 1995; Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023). Compression of the vertical pharyngeal cavity during pharyngealisation increases the frequency of resonant sound waves (Lieberman, 2007) translating to higher F1. This suggests pharyngealised emphatics. However, in studies that find a consistent F1 effect (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011), it is still considerably less noticeable than reduced F2. Other studies (Card, 1983; Kulikov et al., 2020; Norlin, 1987) find no consistent difference in F1. Pharyngeal consonants are also associated with slightly reduced F2. Although this seems to corroborate pharyngealisation, Bukshaisha (1985) found that the effect on F2 was more significant for emphatic than pharyngeal consonants; /a/ was articulated further forward with an F2 of 1500 Hz after /h/, but as back (1000 Hz) after /t/.

Bukshaisha (1985) investigated the production of emphatic consonants in Qatari Arabic. She found two significant effects of emphasis on consonant production: shorter VOT in /t/ than /t/ and a lower spectral mean in emphatic fricatives. /t/ featuring a longer VOT than /t/ is corroborated widely (Alghamdi, 2006; AlDahri, 2012a, 2012b, 2013; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004). Other investigations (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011; Abudaljuh, 2010) disagree with Bukshaisha's (1985) findings. Jongman et al. (2011) instead find that only emphatic plosives have significantly lower spectral mean than their plain counterparts. Strict aerodynamic constraints govern fricative production and do not allow much variation in the shape of the tongue body. Greater tongue backing for emphatic stops (cf. Ghazeli, 1977) means that the length of the front cavity increases more in stops, thus lowering spectral mean only for plosives.

1.1.2 *Spread of Emphatic Features*

There is a consensus that emphatics have significant coarticulatory effects on adjacent segments; most emphatic literature specifically investigates vocalic properties (Ali & Daniloff, 1974; Jongman et al., 2011; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004; Card, 1983). Ali and Daniloff (1974) show the initial consonant of a word may be identified as emphatic even when it was completely truncated. Hence, emphatic coarticulation on adjacent vowels is perceptually salient.

Evidence suggests that rightward spread of emphasis is more constrained than leftward spread (e.g., Watson, 1999; Jaber et al., 2001; Bukshaisha, 1985; Herzallah, 1990; Slimani, 2018). Furthermore, Zawaydeh (1999) showed that (in Ammani Arabic) leftward spread is categorical: F2 is equally low regardless of distance from an emphatic. In contrast, rightward spread was found to be gradient.

The domain of this spread is most often identified as the syllable (Lehn, 1963; Obrecht, 1968; Shaaban, 1977; Sayed, 1981; Algryani, 2014). Brosh (2015) argues that syllabic emphatic spread may be noticeable enough that *sawt* 'whip' is homophonous with *ṣawt* 'sound'. Other studies identify the phonological word as the locus of emphasis spread (Youssef, 2014; Bukshaisha, 1985). Emphasis may spread to previous words (Bukshaisha, 1985), subject to strict locality conditions (Woidich, 2006) and speech rate (Broselow, 1976).

Despite dialectal variation, this section has established that (i) emphatic consonants are uvularized, (ii) cues such as VOT and spectral mean may be salient in emphatic perception, (iii) emphasis spreads variably, triggering backed allophones of adjacent vowels.

1.1.3 *Emphatic Perception I: Perceptual Studies of L1 Arabic Speakers*

Jongman et al. (2011), in a comprehensive study of Urban Jordanian Arabic, used cross-splicing to create intermediary stimuli in which some segments were produced in emphatic context and others in plain context (e.g., an emphatic /s/ followed by the rime /a:b/ produced in plain context). Participants were presented these intermediary stimuli in a forced identification task; they were instructed to indicate whether the stimulus began with an emphatic consonant. Words in which the rime only came from an emphatic context (CVC) elicited 69% emphatic responses. Meanwhile, those in which only the target consonant was emphatic saw 15% emphatic responses, a statistically significant difference. When including all stimuli, words with a primary emphatic target elicited more frequent emphatic responses than those without (53% vs 36%). Stimuli with emphatic rimes (CVC and CVC) elicited 80% emphatic responses whereas those with plain rimes (CVC and CVC) only elicited them 9% of the time. We may suggest the emphatic effect on following segments is a more salient perceptual cue than the initial consonant alone.

When analysing target-final stimuli (e.g., *bas*, *baʕ*), Jongman et al. (2011) observed greater emphatic responses when the initial CV sequence (i.e., the vowel and the non-target consonant) was emphatic (94%) than when the rime of a target-initial word was emphatic (69%)

Jongman et al. (2011) also found manner of articulation differences. They compared responses for the CVC condition between fricatives and plosives. There was no significant difference in emphatic responses between emphatic (48%) and plain (41%) fricatives. Emphatic plosives, however, did elicit significantly greater emphatic responses (60%) than plain ones (28%). This matches their acoustic data, which suggested spectral mean is only significantly lowered in emphatic plosives but not fricatives (*contra* Bukshaisha, 1985).

Although Jongman et al.'s (2011) methodology does not allow for distinctions to be made between the vowel and the non-target consonant (as they were spliced together), they isolate the primary perceptual correlate of emphasis to lowered vocalic F2. Greater lowering of F2 and Yeou (1995)'s findings that F1 alone is not a salient perceptual cue rule out vocalic F1 here. This is seemingly corroborated by evidence that lowered vocalic F2 is a salient cue for emphasis (Aldamen & Al-Deaibes, 2023; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004; Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016). However, crucially, none of these studies measured the effect of the non-target consonant; vocalic F2 alone cannot be confidently identified as the primary cue. If we follow the logic that perception and production are linked, Card's (1983) detailed phonetic analysis of F2 in vowels and non-emphatic consonants shows that F2 lowers in both even if vocalic F2 decreases further. Although this stresses the importance of the vowel, it suggests that coarticulatory effects of the non-target consonant may have been overlooked.

1.1.4 *Emphatic Perceptions II: Perceptual Studies of L2 Arabic Speakers*

Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) replicated the Jongman et al.'s (2011) methodology instead investigating English-speaking learners of Arabic. They collected 'overlap scores' from participants by asking them to identify the closest English vowel phoneme to the Arabic vowel in words with and without emphatics. The overlap score represents the percentage of tokens in which the plain- and emphatic-context vowels are identified to be closest to the same English phoneme. The overlap scores for /i/ (71%) and /u/ (69%) were significantly higher than for /a/ (3%). Low overlap implies English speakers perceive the plain and emphatic allophones of /a/ ([æ] and [ɑ]) as exemplars of separate English phonemes.

As expected, English speakers relied on vowel quality for emphatic distinctions. There was no difference in emphatic responses between target-initial CVC and CVC words (7%); the emphatic consonant had no effect on emphatic responses. When the rime was contextually emphatic, the vowel quality was a good predictor of emphatic responses: /a/ elicited 79% emphatic responses, /u/ 60%, and /i/ only 34%. When plain, /a/ elicited the lowest emphatic responses (2%) compared to /i/ (9%) and /u/

(10%). Participants were most accurate for all stimuli featuring /a/. To confirm that this was due to English vowel phonemes, they repeated the same study with native Arabic speakers who instead reported significantly higher emphatic responses for **ÇYÇ** and **CYÇ** stimuli with /u/ (87%) followed by /a/ (70%) and /i/ (40%). This provides evidence for English speakers using native distinctions to aid in emphatic perception. Self-reported phoneme similarities by English speakers in Zaba (2007) further support this notion; plain-emphatic overlap with English phonemes was lowest for /a/ followed by /u/ then /i/.

1.2 Acquisitional Frameworks

Following the in-depth phonological and phonetic analysis of emphasis in Section 1.1, the pressing matter at hand becomes two-fold: Firstly, (i) what mechanisms do L2 speakers use to distinguish foreign sounds? And (ii) can L2 speakers achieve native-like proficiency, and if so, how? This section will present different acquisitional frameworks and what they predict regarding L2 emphatic perception.

First, we may draw our attention to the Perceptual Assimilation Model (PAM; Best, 1994, 1995; modified to better suit L2 acquisition in Best & Tyler, 2007 as PAM-L2) which suggests that discrimination of some nonnative contrasts may be good without training (Best, 1998) whereas others may require explicit training (Strange & Dittmann, 1984; Pisoni et al., 1982) or extensive naturalistic experience (MacKain et al., 1981; Tees & Werker, 1984; Hayes-Harb, 2007; Enomoto, 1994). Nonnative contrasts are assimilated differently into the L1 phonology, explaining the variable perceptual difficulty observed. There are three relevant types of assimilation: **two-category** (TC) in which a nonnative contrast is assimilated with an existing native contrast (e.g., Tigrinya /t’-/p’/ with English /t-/p/; Best, 1993); **category-goodness** (CG) in which both nonnative sounds are assimilated into the same native category but one is noticeably more deviant from the native ideal (e.g., Zulu /k’-/k’/ as a good and deviant exemplar of English /k/; Best, 1994); and **single-category** (SC) where nonnative sounds are assimilated to the same native category and are equally acceptable (e.g., Thompson Salish /k’-/q’/ both as deviant exemplars of English /k/; Best, 1994). The order of difficulty in acquisition is expected to be TC > CG > SC (Al Mahmoud, 2013).

Emphatic contrasts are likely a CG assimilation (Al Mahmoud, 2013); both are assimilated into the same English phoneme with the emphatic variant noticeably more deviant. Perception of emphatics is thus predicted to be significantly above chance (Pisoni, 1973); Best et al. (2001) found an accuracy of 89.4% for CG in a study of Zulu ejectives. In a perceptual study of /t’-/t’/ and /ð’-/ð’/ contrasts, Al Mahmoud (2013) instead found less accurate discrimination (68.7%; 64.8% for /t’/, 72.7% for /ð’/). Accuracy for /t’-/t’/ is below what is expected by PAM. The reason for this is hypothesised to be that /t’/ is perceived as closer to /t/ than /ð’/ is to /ð/. This is supported by Lababidi and Park (2017) who asked L1 English participants to label Arabic stimuli with an English consonant and rate goodness-of-fit. They found that 37.5% of /t’/ tokens were identified as /t/ (3.3/10 goodness) whereas only 12.5% of /ð’/ tokens were identified as /ð/ (6 goodness). However, their data does not support the overall low accuracy of Al Mahmoud’s participants: 50% of /t’/ tokens were identified as /f/ (5 goodness), a phoneme English speakers should have no trouble discriminating from /t/. Furthermore, /ð’/ was most often identified as an uncategorisable sound (50% of tokens; 4.5 goodness). An uncategorisable sound paired with a categorisable one (/ð’/) should elicit accuracy higher than that found by Al Mahmoud (2013). Liebethal et al. (2003) suggest within-category contrasts are discriminated using acoustic memory traces. Compared to phonemes, these traces are less stable and efficient. However, their stability and efficiency may vary depending on the type of acoustic input. Ejectives feature an almost complete termination of glottal air flow during their release (Best et al., 2001). This acoustic cue could form more stable memory traces than uvularisation for English speakers. Thus, the discriminatory accuracy measures found by Best et al (2001) may be inflated.

One of PAM's central ideas is that gesture is the basis of production and perception. Best (1991) compares this to Psychoacoustic Theory (PT; Diehl & Kluender, 1989) that assumes the immediate object of speech perception is raw acoustic experience whereas speech production is governed by gesture. This creates a mismatch between perception and production which is inconsistent with the clear production-perception link found in emphatic literature (see Sections 1.1.3 and 1.1.4). PAM-L2, instead, assumes that gesture is the basis of both production and perception, creating a solid link. Therefore, PAM's ability to account for perception-production links makes it a suitable model for the purposes of this investigation.

The Extended Native Language Magnet Model (NLM-e; Kuhl et al., 2008) is a similar exemplar-theoretic approach. NLM-e focuses on neural commitment. Given experience with the L1, infants create phonetic categories including perfect and poor examples of each native phoneme (cf. Pierrehumbert, 2001). Such "early exposure to language shapes [...] attentional networks, and [...] in adulthood, they make second language learning difficult" (Kuhl et al., 2008). NLM-e comes together with the Perceptual Magnet Effect (PME) which states that established phonetic categories affect perception and "the best instances of the category are associated with reduced discrimination and perceptual clustering" (Iverson & Kuhl, 1995: 560). For emphatics, the PME predicts that /s/-/ʃ/ and /d/-/ɗ/ may be more difficult to discern as they will both cluster within /s/ and /d/. Whereas /t/-/t̪/ may be slightly easier as the emphatic /t̪/ features considerably lower VOT than /t/ which is usually [t^h] (Bukshaisha, 1985). English voiced plosives are often described as partially voiced (Gonet, 2001; Collins & Mees, 2003), and aspiration is a salient perceptual cue of plosive 'voicing' (Deterding & Nolan, 2007). Therefore, Arabic /t/ and /t̪/ would likely cluster with English /t/ and /d/, facilitating accurate discrimination. Of course, Al Mahmoud (2013) did not find this when compared to /ð/-/ð̪/ but provided no data regarding /s/-/ʃ/ or /d/-/ɗ/. NLM-e also accounts for Hayes-Harb & Durham's (2016) findings regarding /a/ facilitating accurate emphatic perception due to the English /æ/-/ɑ/ distinction. These predictions are similar to those made by PAM-L2.

A point of difference between PAM and NLM-e is the stress of social factors. Although both rightly draw upon principles of statistical learning (Saffran et al., 1996), NLM-e acknowledges centrally the importance of directed speech and teaching in phonological development whereas PAM-L2 does not. For example, Kuhl et al. (2003) found that, when exposed to a new language at age 0;9, infants only learn phonetically from a live interacting human being, but not a disembodied source. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2005) show the importance of directed and exaggerated speech for adult Japanese speakers learning the English /r/-/l/ distinction. In this way, NLM-e predicts participants' experience learning Arabic (e.g., independent study vs. class learning) will have an impact on their perceptual acquisition of emphatics.

1.3 Research Questions and Hypotheses

The purpose of this study is to investigate the auditory cues L2 Arabic speakers use to distinguish emphatic consonants from their plain counterparts. The focus is whether speakers can accurately perceive uvularisation on emphatic consonants themselves or if they rely more heavily on coarticulatory effects on the surrounding segments. The experimental research questions and predictions are as follows:

- (1) Are acoustic cues on surrounding vowels more perceptually salient than those on the primary emphatic?

I predict that contextually emphatic vowels will be associated with higher numbers of emphatic responses (cf. Jongman et al., 2011; Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016 etc.). Phonological primary emphatics will elicit significant (but lower) numbers of emphatic responses. Non-phonologically emphatic consonants spliced from emphatic context will not have a significant effect on responses.

However, a contextually emphatic consonant paired with an emphatic vowel may show interaction effects, enhancing emphatic responses (cf. Jongman et al., 2011). Coarticulated segments in emphatic-final words (i.e., /d/ and /u/ from /duʔ/) may elicit greater proportions of emphatic responses due to increased leftward spread (cf. Herzallah, 1990; Zawaydeh, 1999).

- (2) Does vowel quality have significant effects on the proportion of emphatic responses?

I predict that the emphatic quality of the /a/ vowel will be a significant predictor of responses due to its neutral and backed allophones being assimilated into existing English phonemes (cf. Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016 etc.). I predict that /i/ and /u/ will elicit similar responses but will be more accurate for /u/ (cf. Zaba, 2007).

- (3) Does the manner of articulation of emphatic consonants have significant effects on the proportion of emphatic responses?

I predict that emphatic plosives will elicit higher numbers of emphatic responses than emphatic fricatives due to their significantly different spectral means (cf. Jongman et al., 2011; Abudalbh, 2010 etc.). Stimuli using the /t/-/t̤/ distinction will elicit the highest numbers of correct responses as the Arabic aspirated /t/ [t^h] and unaspirated /t/ [t̤] will be assimilated into the English voicing distinction /t/-/d/ ([t^h]-[t]).

- (4) Do L2 Arabic proficiency and pedagogical background have significant effects on emphatic responses?

I predict that higher Arabic proficiency will be associated with more accurate emphatic perception. Furthermore, highly proficient speakers may display less pronounced vowel quality and aspiration effects due to less reliance on native contrasts. However, consonantal and vocalic effects are still expected.

Participants with extensive immersion backgrounds will show more accurate responses and higher emphatic responses given only a primary emphatic consonant than participants who primarily self-study. Increased spoken Arabic input is likely correlated with more native-like performance on this perception task.

2 Methodology

2.1 Phase 1: Stimulus Generation

2.1.1 Speakers Recorded for Stimuli

Three female native Arabic speakers (ages: 20-28; mean: 23) were recorded with a H4n Pro handheld recorder (96 kHz and 24 bitrate). They are identified with two-letter codes indicating their native dialect: Moroccan (MA), Sudanese (SD), and Egyptian (EG). MA grew up in Morocco, moving to the UK at age 25 (three years prior) and spoke conversational French and rudimentary English; an Arabic-English translator was present. SD lived in Sudan and Qatar, speaking both Arabic dialects, and has lived in the UK for the longest of these countries. EG has lived for the longest in Kuwait, spending significant time in the UAE and Egypt; she moved to the UK for university aged 18 (three years prior). All speakers were instructed to use MSA for recordings.

2.1.2 Recorded Stimuli

The stimuli presented were MSA pseudowords. They were all CVC and obeyed Arabic phonotactic rules. The pseudowords formed minimal pairs as one consonant (the target) differed only by emphasis. They were also formulated so there was one minimal pair of words for each vowel quality (/a/, /i/, and /u/) and target consonant quality (/s/, /t/, and /d/) combination. Due to time constraints, the dental fricatives /ð/-/ð^ˤ/ were excluded (cf. Al-Wer, 2003). Wehr (1952) surveyed triconsonantal roots in Arabic to determine the ranking of most frequent Arabic consonants. The non-target consonant for each pseudoword was the most common consonant that would not form a meaningful MSA word. Uvular and pharyngeal consonants /χ q ħ ʕ/ were excluded, as were /r/ and /l/, due to their potential emphasis-like formant-altering effects (see Section 1.1.1). The letter *ghayn* (غ) is present in two pseudowords where no other consonant would form a non-word (*tagh-tagħ* and *dugh-ḡugh*). It is variably described as velar /ɣ/ or uvular /ʁ/. Based on these constraints, the stimuli are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Experimental pseudowords organised by target consonant and nucleic vowel

		A		I		U	
		Plain	Emphatic	Plain	Emphatic	Plain	Emphatic
S-Ṣ	Initial	سَاش	صَاش	سِيك	صِيك	سُون	صُون
		sāsh	ṣāsh	sik	ṣik	sūn	ṣūn
		sa:ʃ	s ^ˤ a:ʃ	sik	s ^ˤ ik	sun	s ^ˤ u:n
	Final	يَاس	يَاص	بِيس	بِيص	سُس	سُص
		yas	yaṣ	bīs	bīṣ	sus	suṣ
		jas	jaṣ ^ˤ	bi:s	bi:s ^ˤ	sus	sus ^ˤ
T-Ṭ	Initial	تَاع	طَاع	تِي	طِي	تُوج	طُوج
		taġ	ṭaġ	ti2	ṭi2	tūj	ṭūj
		tay	t ^ˤ ay	tiʔ	ṭiʔ	tu:d̤ʒ	t ^ˤ u:d̤ʒ
	Final	تَات	طَات	وَيْت	وَيْط	دُت	دُط
		thāt	ṭhāt	wīt	wīṭ	dut	duṭ
		θa:t	θa:t ^ˤ	wi:t	wi:t ^ˤ	dut	dut ^ˤ
D-Ḍ	Initial	دَز	ضَر	دِيف	ضِيف	دُغ	ضُغ
		daz	ḡaz	dīf	ḡīf	duġ	ḡuġ
		daz	d ^ˤ az	di:f	d ^ˤ i:f	duɣ	d ^ˤ uɣ
	Final	دَد	دَض	ثِد	ثِص	تُود	تُوص
		dhad	dhaḡ	thid	thiḡ	tūd	tūḡ
		ðad	ðad ^ˤ	zid	zid ^ˤ	tu:d	tu:d ^ˤ

Table 3: Distractor pseudowords organised by target consonant and nucleic vowel

		A		I		U	
		Voiceless	Voiced	Voiceless	Voiced	Voiceless	Voiced
S-Z	Initial	سَاش	زَاش	بِسْكَ	زِكْ	سُونْ	زُونْ
		sāsh	zāsh	sik	zik	sūn	zūn
		sa:ʃ	za:ʃ	sik	zik	sun	zu:n
	Final	يَسْ	يَزْ	بِيسْ	بِيزْ	سُسْ	سُزْ
		yas	yaz	bīs	bīz	sus	suz
		jas	jaz	bi:s	bi:z	sus	suz
T-D	Initial	تَغْ	دَغْ	تِيْ	دِيْ	تُوْجْ	دُوْجْ
		taġ	daġ	ti2	di2	tūj	dūj
		taɣ	daɣ	tiʔ	diʔ	tu:d̪ɟ	du:d̪ɟ
	Final	تَاتْ	تَادْ	وَيْتْ	وَيْدْ	دُتْ	دُدْ
		thāt	thād	wīt	wīd	dut	dud
		θa:t	θa:d	wi:t	wi:d	dut	dud
Ṭ-Ḍ	Initial	طَزْ	Ḍَزْ	طَيْفْ	Ḍَيْفْ	طُغْ	Ḍُغْ
		ʔaz	Ḍaz	ʔīf	Ḍīf	ʔuġ	Ḍuġ
		tʕaz	dʕaz	tʕi:f	dʕi:f	tʕuɣ	dʕuɣ
	Final	دَطْ	دَضْ	ثِطْ	ثِضْ	تُوْطْ	تُوْضْ
		dhaʔ	dhaḌ	thiṭ	thiḌ	tūʔ	tūḌ
		ðatʕ	ðadʕ	θitʕ	θidʕ	tu:tʕ	tu:dʕ

Distractor words (Table 3) were also created using the same method, with the plain-emphatic consonant pair replaced with a voiceless-voiced pair. Target consonants of the form /s/-/sʕ/ were replaced with /s/-/z/, /t/-/tʕ/ with /t/-/d/, and /d/-/dʕ/ with /tʕ/-/dʕ/. None of the distractors were meaningful MSA words. Due to concerns of task length, there was only one distractor per three experimental stimuli.

A small selection of real MSA words were also gathered (Table 4). They were used in a short practice trial to aid in familiarity with the experimental task as well as to access the English-speaking learner’s Arabic lexicon and phonology. Six pairs of words were chosen. Two pairs per vowel, one

Table 4: Real Modern Standard Arabic words used as the stimuli for the practice trial

A		I		U	
Plain	Target	Plain	Target	Plain	Target
دَمْ	ضَمْ	تَيْنْ	طَيْنْ	سُمْ	ضُمْ
damm	Ḍamm	tīn	ṭīn	sum	ṣum
dæm:	dʕæm:	ti:n	tʕi:n	sum:	sʕum:
dye	joining	fig	mud	poison	fast!
طَبْ	ضَبْ	سِرْ	زِرْ	تُبْ	دُبْ
ṭabb	Ḍab	sir	zir	tub	dubb
tʕab:	dʕab:	sir	zir	tub	dub:
treatment	cleaving	depart	button	repent	bear

being a plain-emphatic minimal pair, and the other a voiceless-voiced pair. The target consonant was word-initial in all words.

2.1.3 Recording Procedure

Recordings took place in quiet yet convenient spaces for each speaker: MA in an office, SD in a common room, and EG in a secluded library room. Each environment was suitably small and/or padded to minimise echoing. Participants were instructed to read aloud each word three times with small pauses between. The experimenter was present, monitoring the recorded audio using headphones. If any words were unclear or obscured by unavoidable noise, speakers were instructed to repeat. Speakers were paid £7.50 for their participation.

2.1.4 Stimulus Generation

Unedited .wav files of the speakers' recordings were spliced in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2023). The clearest repetition of each word was identified per speaker. Using the spectrogram (Gaussian window) and waveform, each segment was identified. The nucleic vowel was defined by the clear presence of F1. Isolating the vowel allows for the isolation of the onset and coda consonants. Where this was more difficult (e.g., when the onset consonant was a semivowel), the vowel included the formant transition from the initial semivowel, in keeping with the including of formant transitions in the vowel following other consonants (Figure 1).

When a segment was isolated, the 'extract selected sound' feature was used to create Praat objects consisting of individual segments. The same process was repeated for the corresponding plain or emphatic word. These segments were combined using the 'concatenate (with overlap)' feature. An overlap of 0.01 s was used as standard to reduce audible splicing. Where splicing was still evident, the overlap was increased in 0.01 s intervals until the stimulus was as naturalistic as possible while still maintaining distinction between each segment.

Figure 1: wide-band spectrogram of speaker EG uttering /jas/ segmented by formant transitions.

This cross-splicing was done so each possible combination of plain and emphatic segments was accounted for. We may indicate the target consonant with emboldening; compare *sik* and ***şik*** with *dut* and ***duť***. The context is determined by the target consonant. In ***şik***, as the target consonant is emphatic, the VC segments taken from this recording are contextually 'emphatic' (and indicated with an underdot). The possible combinations are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Compass-style figure showing possible splicing patterns using non-words *sik* and *dut* as examples. Emboldened segments are the target consonant (i.e., the consonant that creates the plain-emphatic minimal pairs). An underdot represents a segment produced in emphatic context. Thus, an emboldened and underdotted consonant is an emphatic target.

Experimental conditions are indicated with a code: vPiP refers to the vowel being plain in the context of a plain target consonant (vowel Plain in Plain). Similarly, vEiE is an emphatic vowel in emphatic context. These are congruent as the vowel matches the target. vEiP and vPiE represent an incongruent vowel that is either emphatic in plain, or plain in emphatic, respectively. The same system is used for the non-target consonant by replacing *v* with *c* (i.e., cPiP, cEiE, cEiP, cPiE). Therefore, for each pseudoword, there are eight stimuli created. The fully congruent stimuli (CVC or ÇVC) were also created via same-splicing.

2.2 Phase 2: Perception Experiment

2.2.1 Participants

Recruitment was carried out via email. Requests for circulation were sent to 56 institutions – including UK, US, and Arabic-speaking universities; Arab and/or Islamic societies; and Middle Eastern studies research institutions. The link for the experiment was also sent via word-of-mouth to other Arabic speakers or learners.

12 participants completed the experiment (ages: 19-25; mean: 21.5). Of these, seven were female and five male. 11 of the 12 participants were native English speakers who have lived most of their life in the UK. Only one was a native Arabic speaker from Lebanon. All English-speaking participants received taught Arabic classes, eight of whom indicated classes as their primary form of learning. Seven of 11 indicated having protracted immersion opportunities. The mode CEFR proficiency was B2 (n=4), followed by B1 and A2 (both n=3), and C2 (n=2, including the native speaker). All participants spoke MSA; the most common other dialect spoken was Levantine (n=6), followed by Egyptian (n=2), and Gulf (n=1).

2.2.2 Procedure

To reach a wider audience, the experiment was carried out online. It consisted of a background questionnaire in the participant's native language (Arabic or English) followed by a pseudoword discrimination task. Both the questionnaire and discrimination task were created using Gorilla (www.gorilla.sc) software (Anwyl-Irvine et al., 2020). Data was collected between 20 December 2023 and 7 February 2024.

Ethical approval for this experiment was awarded by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Modern and Medieval Languages and Linguistics at the University of Cambridge on October 16, 2023.

2.2.3 Questionnaires

Participants were asked to identify their native language. This determined the language of instruction for the rest of the experiment. Arabic and English speakers received differing questionnaires, both of which were used to screen participants. Both questionnaires gathered information regarding age, country of origin, gender, consent, and any speech or hearing impairments. Arabic-speaking participants were also instructed to identify their native dialect. English-speaking participants were prompted to provide information regarding Arabic proficiency, primary method of learning Arabic, which dialects they have studied, and their confidence in reading Arabic script.

Participants were excluded from the study based on the information provided in the questionnaires. 11 participants were rejected this way: four minors; three unconfident readers; three speakers with a native language other than Arabic or English; and one with a hearing impairment. From the beginning of the first questionnaire, an 8-hour timer begins. When this ends, participants are automatically rejected if they have not completed the entire experiment. 37 people were rejected this way.

2.2.4 Experimental Design

After completing the questionnaires, participants are redirected to a forced identification task, also hosted on Gorilla. Participants were instructed that the experimental task should be completed in a quiet room wearing headphones and, ideally, on a desktop or laptop computer rather than a mobile phone. The task worked on mobile phones, but issues of text size rendered them suboptimal.

Gorilla features an in-built sound test. Participants were played a short recording of a voice saying "one, two, three" and are asked if they heard the sound clearly. If not, participants were instructed to adjust any parameters and try the sound test again. Only participants that successfully heard the test audio were allowed access to complete the task.

The experiment took the form of a forced identification task. Participants were played an audio file. After the file had been fully played, they were then prompted to identify, out of the two vowelised Arabic-script options on screen, how they would spell the audio. All vowel diacritics (*ḥarakāt*) were included as, without them, there may have been a mismatch between the audio stimuli and how the participants initially read the pseudowords. The two options differed only in the emphasis of one consonant. They could choose either option via a button press or by clicking. When one option was chosen, a buffer screen was shown, allowing for participants to take short breaks if they wished. The next audio would play when a continue button was pressed. No feedback was given to participants at any point. Halfway through the task, there was a dedicated break that participants were encouraged to take for about five minutes to keep their reactions sharp.

Please indicate how you would spell the word in the audio clip.

Figure 3: Screenshot of a Gorilla screen featuring a forced binary identification task with the options being the vowelised Arabic-script pseudowords *dhad* and *dhaḍ*, respectively.

2.2.5 Data Analysis

Participants’ responses to each audio stimulus are recorded. Indicating the audio as the word spelled without an emphatic consonant (e.g., < <دَد/ḍad/ in Figure 3) would be recorded as *plain* whereas inputting the other option (e.g., < <دَض/ḍaḍ/) would elicit the response *target*. These responses were compared against whether the target consonant was emphatic in the audio to isolate if the emphatic judgement was correct or not. These responses are the primary data presented and analysed in Section 3.

3 Results

Unless specified otherwise, the following results are calculated from the 11 L2 participants as intergroup comparisons are not feasible given the significant asymmetry in recruitment.

3.1 Effects of Emphatic Coarticulation by Segment

3.1.1 Analysis

Results for percentage emphatic responses across all stimuli are shown in Figure 4. The highest proportion of emphatic responses was observed for **ÇYÇ** (68.25%). This is followed by **ÇYÇ** (67.34%). The lowest proportion of emphatic responses was observed for **CVC** stimuli (26.06%) with **CVC** being similar (27.04%). 48.52% of stimuli elicited an emphatic response.

A three-way repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables showed main effects for Vowel [$F(1,7)=538.24$, $p=0.027$]. Neither Target [$F(1,7)=85.87$, $p=0.068$] nor Non-Target Consonants [$F(1,7)=1.14$, $p=0.479$] alone showed significant effects. No significant interaction effects were observed.

Post hoc paired G-tests (cf. Ahad et al., 2019) were performed for each Splice Type pair (Table 5). All pairs, bar four, showed significant differences in emphatic responses [all $p<0.001$].

Figure 4: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentages of emphatic responses elicited by each splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. ÇVC indicates stimuli in which only the target primary emphatic is emphatic; CVC when only the vowel is emphatic; and CVC when only the non-target consonant is emphatic. The following conditions follow this convention.

All four pairs in which significant effects were not observed featured manipulation of the non-target consonant.

Significant differences were found between stimuli in which only the target was emphatic (ÇVC; 38.64%) and when only the vowel was emphatic (CVC; 58.47%) [$G(1)=46.753$, $p<0.001$]. These were also found between ÇVC and ÇVC (68.25%) [$G(1)=105.455$, $p<0.001$].

Table 5: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each splice type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance

	ÇVC	CVC	CVC	ÇVC	ÇVC	CVC	CVC	CVC
ÇVC		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.093	0.000	0.000	0.000
CVC			0.000	0.000	0.000	0.913	0.002	0.000
CVC				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.702
ÇVC					0.000	0.001	0.739	0.000
CVC						0.000	0.000	0.000
CVC							0.002	0.000
CVC								0.000
CVC								

3.1.2 Word-Initial Targets

Emphatic responses when target-initial are shown in Figure 5. The highest average percentage of emphatic responses was again found for TVÇ (72.3%) with the entirely emphatic TVÇ falling behind (70.95%). Similarly to the overall data, TVC elicited the lowest number of emphatic responses (27.03%). 51.18% of all stimuli elicited emphatic responses.

A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables indicated a significant main effect for Vowel [$F(1,7)=1521$, $p=0.016$] and Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=174.24$, $p=0.048$]. No significant effect was observed for

Figure 5: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentage of emphatic responses elicited by each target-initial splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. *T* represents the target consonant.

Non-Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=0.64$, $p=0.57$]. No significant interaction effects were observed.

P-values from post hoc G-tests can be found in Table 6. Five pairs showed no significant difference. Four of these were also found in the overall data (Section 3.1.1). However, T \bar{V} C and T \bar{V} Ċ showed no significant difference [$G(1)=3.505$, $p=0.061$]. T \bar{V} Ċ-T \bar{V} Ċ showed marginally significant effects [$G(1)=3.934$, $p=0.047$]. This was checked with a Fisher’s Exact Test – which is more appropriate for the smaller sample sizes of each pair (cf. Jung, 2014) – which returned the results as insignificant ($p=0.052$).

Table 6: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each Splice Type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance. Yellow-highlighted values indicate a p-value that was determined as insignificant post G-test

P	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC
TVC		0.000	0.001	0.000	0.452	0.000	0.000	0.001
TVC			0.000	0.025	0.000	0.913	0.061	0.000
TVC				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.783
TVC					0.000	0.019	0.715	0.000
TVC						0.000	0.000	0.000
TVC							0.047	0.003
TVC								0.000
TVC								

3.1.3 Word-Final Targets

When examining only target-final words, similar trends were observed. CVT stimuli elicited the higher proportion of emphatic responses (64.16%). CVT elicited the lowest (25.08%) followed by ÇVT (26.03%). 45.84% of target-final stimuli elicited emphatic responses.

A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables observed a significant main effect for Vowel context [$F(1,7)=538.24$, $p=0.027$]. No significant effects were found for Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=85.87$, $p=0.068$] or Non-Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=1.138$, $p=0.479$]. No significant interaction effects were observed.

Figure 6: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentage of emphatic responses elicited by each target-final splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. T represents the target consonant.

Post hoc G-tests indicated most pairs as significant, excluding the same four insignificant pairs found in both Section 3.1.1 and Section 3.1.2. Target-final stimuli elicited significantly different responses in

the **CV̇T-CV̇Ṫ** [$G(1)=6.722, p=0.01$] and **ÇV̇T-ÇV̇Ṫ** [$G(1)=5.502, p=0.019$] pairs (unlike for target-initial words).

Table 7: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each Splice Type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance

P	CV̇Ṫ	CV̇T	ÇV̇Ṫ	ÇV̇T	CV̇Ṫ	ÇV̇Ṫ	CV̇Ṫ	CV̇T
CV̇Ṫ		0.000	0.005	0.000	0.103	0.000	0.000	0.002
CV̇T			0.000	0.007	0.017	0.805	0.010	0.000
ÇV̇Ṫ				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.793
ÇV̇T					0.000	0.014	0.913	0.000
CV̇Ṫ						0.008	0.000	0.000
ÇV̇Ṫ							0.019	0.000
CV̇Ṫ								0.000
CV̇T								

G-tests were also performed between complementary target-initial and -final conditions (e.g., between **ṪVC** and **CV̇Ṫ**). The pairs in which significant differences were observed are as follows: **ṪVC-CV̇Ṫ** [$G(1)=6.722, p=0.01$], **ṪVC-CV̇Ṫ** [$G(1)=4.504, p=0.034$], and **ṪVC-ÇV̇Ṫ** [$G(1)=5.024, p=0.025$]. In all cases, the target-final condition showed fewer emphatic responses. This is perhaps due to final targets eliciting fewer emphatic responses overall [$G(1)=13.498, p<0.001$].

Table 8: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for comparison of complementary target-initial (horizontal) and target-final (vertical) pairs

P VALUE	ṪVC	ṪVC	ṪVĊ	ṪVC	ṪVĊ	ṪVĊ	ṪVĊ	ṪVC
CV̇Ṫ	0.362							
CV̇T		0.010						
ÇV̇Ṫ			0.583					
ÇV̇T				0.034				
CV̇Ṫ					0.971			
ÇV̇Ṫ						0.025		
CV̇Ṫ							0.061	
CV̇T								0.591

3.2 Effects of Vowel Quality

Vowel quality effects when both consonants are plain were examined. A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Length, and Emphasis as the independent variables was carried out. Significant main effects were observed for Emphasis [$F(1,9)=40.4, p=0.024$]. Neither Length [$F(1,9)=4.971, p=0.156$] nor Quality [$F(1,9)=0.021, p=0.979$] showed significant effects. No interaction effects were observed.

Figure 7: Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by vowel quality when both consonants are plain.

Post hoc G-tests found significant differences in emphatic responses between plain /a/ (19.7%) and plain /u/ (30.96%) [$G(1)=6.672$, $p=0.01$]. This originally held for their emphatic counterparts /a/ (63.45%) and /u/ (53.3%) [$G(1)=4.186$, $p=0.041$]. However, a Fisher's exact test disqualified this pair as significant ($p=0.052$).

Table 9: Post hoc G-test showing p-values for each vowel pair in CYC

P Value	A	ʌ	ɪ	ɪ̃	U	ʊ
A		0.000	0.066	0.000	0.010	0.000
ʌ			0.000	0.331	0.000	0.041
ɪ				0.000	0.457	0.000
ɪ̃					0.000	0.283
U						0.000
ʊ						

Vowel quality effects were also analysed such that both consonants were not required to be plain. A three-way repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Length, and Emphasis as the independent variables was carried out. Again, only Emphasis showed significant main effects [$F(1,9)=69.32$, $p=0.014$]; neither Length [$F(1,9)=8.52$, $p=0.1$] nor Quality [$F(1,9)=0.119$, $p=0.894$] showed significant effects.

Post hoc G-tests found plain /a/ to elicit significantly fewer emphatic responses (27.32%) than /i/ (34.39%) [$G(1)=9.245$, $p=0.002$] and /u/ (39.72%) [$G(1)=27.203$, $p<0.001$]. The difference between /i/ and /u/ was also significant [$G(1)=4.784$, $p=0.029$]. /a/ elicited significantly higher emphatic responses (69%) than /i/ (60.86%) [$G(1)=11.447$, $p=0.001$] and /u/ (59.77%) [$G(1)=14.642$, $p<0.001$]. However, the difference between /i/ and /u/ was not significant [$G(1)=0.196$, $p=0.658$].

Table 10: Post hoc G-test results displaying p-values for each vowel quality pair across all splice types

P Value	A	ʌ	ɪ	ɪ̃	U	ʊ
A		0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
ʌ			0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
ɪ				0.000	0.029	0.000
ɪ̃					0.000	0.658
U						0.000
ʊ						

Post hoc G-tests also showed significant effects of length only when the emphatic context of the surrounding consonants was not controlled. Long plain /a:/ elicited fewer emphatic responses (22.73%) than short /a/ (30.27%) [$G(1)=5.456$, $p=0.019$]. Long emphatic /i:/ also elicited fewer emphatic responses (56.6%) than its short counterpart (65.14%) [$G(1)=6.035$, $p=0.014$]. No other pairs showed length effects.

Figure 8: Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by vowel quality across all splice types.

3.3 Effects of Manner of Articulation

Similar analyses were performed given target consonant quality. First, we focus on target consonants where both the vowel and non-target consonant are plain. A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Emphasis, and Position as the independent variables was executed. Significant main effects were observed for Quality [$F(2,11)=81.242$, $p=0.012$] and Emphasis [$F(1,11)=60.176$, $p=0.162$]. No significant effects were observed for Position [$F(1,11)=2.813$, $p=0.235$]. Significant interaction effects were observed only for Quality*Emphasis [$F(2,11)=31$, $p=0.031$].

Post hoc G-tests identified that there was no significant difference between emphatic responses for plain /s/ (21.43%) and emphatic /s/ (19.39%) [$G(1)=0.251$, $p=0.616$]. There were significant differences between the other emphatic pairs: /t/ (16.67%) with /t/ (45.69%) [$G(1)=39.913$,

Figure 9: bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by manner of articulation when vowel and non-target consonants are plain.

$p < 0.001$] and /d/ (40.10%) with /d̥/ (50.76%) [$G(1)=4.524, p=0.033$]. /s/ and /t/ showed no significant difference [$G(1)=1.452, p=0.228$] whereas /s/ elicited significantly fewer emphatic responses than /d/ [$G(1)=16.273, p < 0.001$]. /t/ and /d/ also showed significant differences [$G(1)=27.303, p < 0.001$]. When emphatic, /s/ and /t/ elicited significantly different responses [$G(1)=31.622, p < 0.001$]; /s/ and /d/ did as well [$G(1)=43.609, p < 0.001$]. /t/ and /d̥/ were not significantly different [$G(1)=1.017, p=0.313$].

When the same ANOVA was executed on consonantal data across all splice types, both Quality [$F(2,11)=104.83, p=0.009$] and Emphasis [$F(1,11)=133.941, p=0.007$] showed significant effects, as did their interaction [$F(2,60)=4.718, p=0.012$]. Here, Position showed significant effects [$F(1,11)=29.289, p=0.032$]. Again, only Quality*Emphasis displayed interaction effects [$F(2,11)=37.853, p=0.026$].

Post hoc G-tests showed similar patterns of significance. However, where /s/ and /t/ did not display significant differences when all segments were plain, they did when this is not controlled [$G(1)=15.622, p < 0.001$]. Similarly, /t/ and /d/ also showed significant differences [$G(1)=11.107, p=0.001$]. G-tests showed significant differences of position only for /s/-/s̥/: initial /s/ elicited significantly higher numbers of emphatic responses [$G(1)=5.406, p=0.02$]; this was also true for the emphatic /s/ [$G(1)=7.758, p=0.005$].

Table 11: *post hoc G-tests results showing p-values for each consonantal pair in CVC*

P Value	S	Ṣ	T	Ṫ	D	Ḍ
S		0.616	0.228	0.000	0.000	0.000
Ṣ			0.482	0.000	0.000	0.000
T				0.000	0.000	0.000
Ṫ					0.263	0.313
D						0.033
Ḍ						

Figure 10: *Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by manner of articulation of the target consonant across all splice types.*

3.4 Effects of Arabic Proficiency

3.4.1 L1 Arabic Speaker

Paired G-tests were executed to compare correct and incorrect responses across all trials per participant. The L1 speaker produced the highest number of correct responses (61.34%). However, this was only significantly greater than five of the 11 other participants: two B2 speakers, one B1, and one A2. In fact, the three most accurate participants were native, B1 (61.25% correct) and A2 (60.88%). So, counterintuitively, the native speaker was on par with many L2 speakers.

A series of Fisher's exact tests were performed comparing the mean and median frequency of emphatic and plain responses per splice type of the L2 speakers with the responses of the L1 speaker. Only two splice types showed significant differences: **CVC** ($p=0.024$) and **CVC** ($p=0.004$) in both cases with the native speaker giving significantly fewer emphatic responses. However, in both cases, there were at least three L2 speakers that had comparable results; these L2 speakers represented A2, B1, and B2 proficiency groups.

3.4.2 L2 Arabic Speakers

L2 speakers were organised into two proficiency groups: low proficiency (A2 and B1) and high proficiency (B2-C2). A two-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Splice Type and Proficiency as the independent variables was carried out. Both Splice Type [$F(7,80)=33$, $p<0.001$] and Proficiency [$F(1,80)=6.927$, $p=0.01$] displayed significant differences. There was no significant interaction [$F(7,80)=0.409$, $p=0.894$]. High proficiency speakers produced fewer emphatic responses overall. Post hoc G-tests suggest this difference is only significant for **CVC** [$G(1)=7.359$, $p=0.007$] and **CVC** [$G(1)=5.454$, $p=0.02$] with high proficiency speakers showing fewer emphatic responses.

Figure 11: bar chart depicting percentage correct responses per participant. Red/orange participants are low proficiency; green are high proficiency. Red participants are A, orange are B1, light green are B2, darker green are C2 and native.

Another ANOVA with Splice Type and Proficiency as the independent variables with number of correct responses as the dependent variable was executed. Significant effects were observed for Splice Type [$F(7,80)=27.978$, $p<0.001$] but not for Proficiency [$F(7,80)=0.693$, $p=0.408$]. No interaction was observed.

3.5 Summary of Results

A short summary of results as relevant to the research questions outlined in Section 1.3 follows:

- (1) Stimuli in which the target and vowel were contextually emphatic showed the highest number of emphatic responses: **ÇVC** (68%) and **ÇVÇ** (67%). Stimuli in which the vowel was emphatic elicited higher proportions of emphatic responses compared to corresponding stimuli in which the vowel was plain. This is also true, to a lesser extent, with target consonants: **CVC** showed 58% emphatic responses compared to **ÇVC** with 68%.
- (2) There were significant effects of vowel quality on emphatic responses. Vowel length had no effect. From the highest emphatic responses to the lowest, vowels create the following hierarchy **A >> I >= U >> U >> I >> A** where **>>** indicates a significant difference. Accuracy was highest for /a/ and lowest for /u/.
- (3) Consonants showed manner of articulation effects. /d/ elicited significantly higher emphatic responses regardless of its emphatic status. /s/-/ʃ/ showed no significant differences with all participants producing low emphatic responses. Participants were most accurate perceiving /t/. The hierarchy of accuracy follows as **t-ṭ >> d-ḍ >= s-ʃ**.
- (4) CEFR proficiency had no effect on emphatic responses. The one native speaker, although being the most accurate, was on par with other speakers of varying CEFR proficiencies. Immersion had no significant effect either.

4 Discussion

4.1 Is Consonantal Pharyngealisation Perceptually Salient?

The goal of this study was to examine the acoustic cues of emphasis for native English speakers learning Arabic. Cross-splicing pseudoword stimuli allows for the perceptual effects of different segments to be investigated in isolation and with interactions. Significant (or lack thereof) differences between splice types may reveal which segments L2 speakers attend to for emphatic discrimination.

Looking first at the role of the emphatic target consonant, we see that **ÇVC** stimuli elicited significantly more emphatic responses (39%) compared to the entirely plain **CVC** control (26%). When the vowel and non-target consonant were not controlled, the addition of the emphatic target increased emphatic responses by about 10-15% (e.g., **CVC** elicited 27% emphatic responses compared to **ÇVÇ**'s 43%; or **CVC**'s 58% compared to **ÇVC**'s 68%). This provides evidence that L2 speakers attend to acoustic cues of uvularisation on the phonological emphatic itself.

However, perhaps the primary emphatic is less perceptually salient than acoustic effects on adjacent vowels. **CVC** stimuli elicited 58% emphatic responses compared to the plain **CVC** control (26%). An emphatically coarticulated vowel increased emphatic responses across all conditions. Unlike the target emphatic though, this increase was generally around 25-30%. For example, **CVC** stimuli elicited 27% emphatic responses, compared to **CVC**'s 59%; **ÇVC** elicited 39% emphatic responses whereas the stimuli with an emphatic vowel (**ÇVC**) elicited the highest emphatic responses at 68%. Furthermore, when only one segment was spliced from emphatic context, both **ÇVC** and **CVC** showed below chance emphatic responses (39% and 27%, respectively), whereas **CVC** elicited 58%. Therefore, we may suggest that, although L2 speakers attend to acoustic cues on the emphatic consonant, the coarticulatory effects on the adjacent vowel are more perceptually salient.

Previous studies using a similar methodology do not separate the vowel and non-target consonant. The present study separated these variables to analyse their independent effects. As expected, the non-target consonant had no significant effects on emphatic responses whereas the vowel's emphatic status was the most accurate predictor of responses. This provides further evidence for the notion that the

emphatic effect on adjacent vowels is the most perceptually salient cue (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011; Ali & Daniloff, 1974; Card, 1983; Yeou, 1995). Thus, consonantal pharyngealisation (or, truly, uvularisation) may not be a particularly salient cue for L2 Arabic speakers' emphatic perception.

Brief attention in data analysis was paid to the role of emphatic spread. Vowels were spliced as such to include the formant transitions of their flanking consonants. Therefore, one may assume that, if emphasis spread is more significant leftwards (cf. Watson, 1999; Jaber et al., 2001; Bukshaisha, 1985; Herzallah, 1990; Slimani, 2018), emphatic vowels and initial non-target consonants from target-final stimuli would elicit a greater facilitative effect on emphatic responses compared to their target-initial counterparts. Quantitative analysis suggests this is not the case: **TVÇ** stimuli elicited 28% emphatic responses whereas **ÇVT** stimuli only elicited 26%. This was not significant. Both **TVÇ** and **ÇVT** elicited 43% emphatic responses and G-tests reveal a significant increase in emphatic responses for **TVÇ** (63%) than **ÇVT** (54%) stimuli. This is not consistent with Jongman et al.'s (2011) findings that **ÇVT** elicited greater emphatic responses (94%) compared to **TVÇ** (69%). Although not designed to assess emphasis spread, the present study tentatively provides evidence to the contrary of more significant leftward spread. However, Zawaydeh (1999) suggests that the primary difference between left- and rightward spread is that leftward spread is categorical whereas rightward is gradient which cannot be assessed with **CVC** stimuli.

4.2 Vowel Quality, Manner of Articulation, and Phonological Acquisition

Segmental quality had significant effects on participant responses. L2 participants were significantly more accurate with their emphatic judgements when the nucleic vowel was /a/ (69% emphatic when /a/; 27% when /a/), whereas /u/ was the most difficult (60% emphatic when /u/; 40% when /u/). This provides evidence to Hayes-Harb and Durham's (2016) suggestion that English speakers make use of their native /a/-/æ/ distinction to differentiate Arabic emphasis. PAM-L2 predicts this as /a/ and /a/ would be a two-category assimilation which is associated with highly accurate perception. Whereas /u/-/u/ would likely be category-goodness (with less accurate discrimination) as /u/ is not acoustically very close to the English /u/. /i/-/i/ could be either, dependent on whether /i/ is assimilated with English /i/ or /i/, explaining its intermediate accuracy. Zaba (2007) and Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) suggest that /i/ is most regularly assimilated with /i/ rather than /i/ which may explain why accuracy was lower for /i/ than /a/. Long /i:/ may be more likely to assimilate as English /i:/, hence explaining why /i:/ elicited fewer emphatic responses than its short counterpart. However, these assimilation patterns cannot be uncritically assumed to hold in the present study as the current finding that participants were least accurate for /u/ is not corroborated by these investigations.

However, Best et al. (2001) found correct discrimination of above 90% for TC assimilation. This is corroborated for vowel phonemes by Tyler et al. (2014). Echoing somewhat Al Mahmoud's (2013) argument, perhaps this is indicative of orthographic effects. Best et al. (2001) and Tyler et al. (2014) use naïve listeners in their perceptual studies. These speakers all used alphabetic writing systems for their native languages. As the vocalic distinction between [a] and [æ] in Arabic is (i) not usually written and (ii) not part of explicit Arabic teaching (unlike the vocalic distinctions between e.g., /a/ and /i/), it is possible that L2 speakers have become entrenched in their formal phonological teaching (cf. McCandliss et al., 2002; Ellis, 2006) and attend to certain vocalic cues less accurately as they would in English. Perhaps this is an issue with PAM-L2. It aims to attribute levels of discrimination to different forms of assimilation. Different assimilation types are difficult to empirically identify; factors such as the individual phonemes, participant differences, and other methodological concerns may render the identification of specific discrimination percentages unreliable. NLM-e, on the other hand, also correctly predicts highest accuracy for /a/-/a/ but does not attempt to provide an absolute range of discrimination, instead taking a relative approach.

Significant effects of consonantal quality were also found. Particularly, the /s/-/ʃ/ distinction was the most difficult for participants. This follows from Jongman et al.'s (2011) and Abudalbh's (2010) findings regarding emphatic fricatives not differing in spectral mean from their plain counterparts (*contra* Bukshaisha, 1985). The equally low number of emphatic responses for both /s/ and /ʃ/ suggests both were assimilated into the plain /s/ as a single-category (SC) assimilation. Low accuracy is explained by both PAM-L2 and NLM-e. But PAM-L2 may be circular. The identification of /s/-/ʃ/ as SC assimilation is due to participants' inaccuracy, which is, in turn, a predictor of SC assimilation. PAM-L2 attempts to make specific predictions but lacks an empirical metric by which to identify assimilation types.

The highest accuracy for /t/-/t̤/ is explainable via aspiration. We may take the view that aspiration is the primary perceptual cue for voicing in English plosives (Deterding & Nolan, 2007) and that Arabic /t/-/t̤/ differ in VOT. Thus, English speakers may use VOT cues to aid in the differentiation of /t/ and /t̤/. G-test analysis of distractor responses showed /t̤/ elicits significantly greater voiced responses (23%) than /t/ (4%) [$G(1)=57.288$, $p<0.001$]. Although voiced responses for /t̤/ were still significantly less frequent than those of /d/ (91%) or /d̤/ (87%), partial assimilation of /t̤/ as voiced as opposed to the solidly voiceless and aspirated /t/ may have contributed to the relative accuracy of responses. In such a case, this provides some evidence that L2 speakers make use of native distinctions even when not phonemic; they attend to different dimensions of the same stimulus (Iverson et al., 2003). This again provides evidence for NLM-e as the Perceptual Magnet Effect would be less pronounced for /t/-/t̤/ than /s/-/ʃ/ and /d/-/d̤/. PAM-L2 may also explain these patterns but, again, the exact percentage of accurate discrimination is still not consistent with the theory's assumptions.

4.3 Proficiency and Pedagogical Background

Overall, participants showed difficulty in identifying emphatic consonants. Comparisons between L1 and L2 participants cannot be drawn due to the unequal sample sizes. So, if we compare the results with those of Jongman et al. (2011), we may see that the L2 participants (as well as the one native speaker) displayed considerably less accurate responses. Jongman et al.'s L1 participants produced 90% emphatic responses for **ÇYÇ** stimuli and only 3% when plain **CVC**. The present study observed a significant difference between these two conditions but L2 speakers only produced 67% emphatic responses for **ÇYÇ** and 26% for **CVC**. These results are consistent with Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) who focused on L2 Arabic speakers who displayed 61% emphatic responses for **ÇYÇ** and 7% for **CVC**. Thus, even in high proficiency cases, L2 Arabic speakers show difficulty reaching native-level emphatic perception. NLM-e predicts overall lower discrimination than PAM-L2 as neural commitment to the L1 renders the exemplar network of phonemes resistant to change. Whereas PAM-L2 assumes extremely high accuracy for TC and CG assimilations (around >90% and >75%, respectively). This may be a strength of NLM-e given the present study's results.

The significantly less accurate performance of the L1 speaker compared with those found by Jongman et al. (2011) may have multiple causes. Firstly, this study uses entirely non-words. Therefore, participants do not have access to a mental lexicon with which they may bolster their emphatic judgements. This has the strength of not disadvantaging L2 participants that may have a smaller vocabulary than native or high proficiency participants. However, this may have affected the performance of the L1 speaker. Secondly, there is no information about their language history beyond being a first language speaker; it is possible they moved to a non-Arabic speaking country at an early age and thus experienced attrition of their language abilities. However, studies of heritage speakers and international adoptees suggest early exposure to a language increases accuracy of phoneme perception into adulthood even if they cannot speak the language (e.g., Oh et al., 2010, Tees & Werker, 1984). Emphatic consonants are not normally masterfully acquired by L1 speakers until at least age 6;4 (Amayreh & Dyson, 1998); if the L1 speaker stopped primarily speaking Arabic at a very young age, it

is perhaps not surprising that their accuracy was low. Due to the lack of available comparisons with other L1 speakers, it is more prudent to treat their results as an anomaly.

NLM-e places heavy emphasis on the style of input. Exaggerated acoustic cues are found to be helpful for first language acquisition (e.g., Maye et al., 2002) as well as in adult classroom settings (cf. Odisho, 2005). This investigation cannot shed light on the role of classroom teaching as all participants received classes. No significant effect of immersion was found, so we may cast some doubt upon the notion that immersion is an effective method of learning such difficult phoneme distinctions. Perhaps the effect of ambient input is significantly reduced once adulthood is reached as the brain has already neurally committed to the L1.

5 Conclusions

The present study examined L2 Arabic speakers' perception of intermediary spliced pseudoword stimuli in a forced identification paradigm.

The results suggest that English speakers show considerable difficulty accurately identifying emphatic consonants even in naturalistic stimuli. English speakers attend primarily to acoustic cues on the adjacent vowels of emphatic consonants to make emphatic judgements; the acoustics of the consonant alone are not always adequate in producing emphatic responses. Thus, consonantal pharyngealisation and/or uvularisation is not fully sufficient for emphatic perception.

Particularly, the present study provides evidence that English speakers make partial use of native phonemic distinctions to aid in emphatic perception. Aspiration distinctions for English plosives and the /æ/-/ɑ/ distinction are the most relevant here.

Accuracy in emphatic responses is presented as highly individual as neither proficiency nor pedagogical background displayed significant effects between participants. These trends are in line with both PAM-L2 and NLM-e. But the overall lower accuracy of participants suggests NLM-e may be more suitable.

5.1 Limitations and Future Research

Limitations of the present study have been addressed where relevant in Section 4. Here, the most important limitations are again summarised.

First, the number of participants surveyed is low. This renders quantitative analysis less reliable. Issues caused by a small sample size are exemplified in the low accuracy of the L1 Arabic speaker surveyed. The causes of their relatively poor performance cannot be known given the information collected. In the Arabic questionnaire, questions could have been included that probed the participants' language history more closely. However, the performance of this participant could not have been anticipated given previous similar studies.

The lack of participants also has ramifications for analysis of pedagogy and proficiency. Controlling such complicated variables to allow for more consistent and valid analysis is difficult given this sample. As NLM-e stresses the type of input in language acquisition, the lack of control in these areas may partially compromise the evidence found in favour of the model. Furthermore, proficiency was self-reported using CEFR guidelines which was originally developed for European languages. Thus, CEFR accuracy for Arabic may be inadequate (cf. Bellassen, 2011) and self-report results are not always reliable.

This study presented participants with pseudoword stimuli. This may have contributed to the overall low accuracy of responses as participants could not use their repertoire of lexical items to aid in perception. All stimuli were CVC and thus the effects of emphasis across larger domains could not be properly evaluated. Finally, as each stimulus had to form two minimal pairs (an experimental emphatic pair and a distractor voicing pair) while also being nonwords, the potential forms these pseudowords

could have taken was significantly constrained. Therefore, some uvular consonants (specifically /ʁ/) had to be included. The F2 lowering effect of the uvular may have had confounding effects on the coarticulatory effect of the uvularised emphatic.

Finally, the method of administration (i.e., online on different devices) may have had limiting effects on the cross-participant reliability of responses due to device limitations (cf. Anwyl-Irvine et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2018; and Woods et al., 2015) and/or environmental distractors. Latency with this method particularly devalues response time data.

Future investigations should address the above concerns. The scope of the study could be extended to include a more controlled comparison of proficiency and pedagogy to evaluate NLM-e and the role of teaching in perceptual acquisition. Expanding the methodology to include polysyllabic real words could increase the understanding of perceptual acquisition in more naturalistic scenarios. Perhaps accurate response time data could be analysed to assess processing difficulties.

6 References

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